

Influence of gallium content on luminescence properties of Ce-doped yttrium aluminum gallium garnet scintillator

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The influence of gallium content in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ on the luminescence properties of this scintillator was studied in a set of Czochralski-grown single crystals with Ga content x varied in the range from 0 to 1. Time-resolved photoluminescence (PL) and cathodoluminescence (CL) spectroscopies were exploited, and temperature dependences of PL properties were studied. A sublinear increase of CL intensity as the excitation intensity increases was observed. The activation energies for thermal quenching in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with Ga content x up to 0.6 were estimated. An increase in the light yield observed with increasing x up to ~ 0.6 , despite the decreasing activation energy for thermal quenching, at the resonant excitation to the emitting $5d_1$ level of Ce^{3+} is interpreted by an additional mechanism enhancing the Ce^{3+} emission. The ratio between the luminescence decay time and the light yield, which is a figure of merit for fast timing properties, is improved with increasing Ga content up to ~ 0.5 .

1. Introduction

Cerium ions Ce^{3+} are efficient activators in garnets, oxyorthosilicates and other crystalline host matrixes to fabricate scintillation materials for the detectors of ionizing radiation. An extremely high internal quantum efficiency of 99.5% has been reported at resonant excitation of Ce^{3+} ions in yttrium aluminum garnet ($Y_3Al_5O_{12}$, YAG) [1]. YAG:Ce phosphor is the wavelength converter of choice in the billions-dollar-market of white light-emitting diodes that are based on InGaN chips with blue emission at 465 nm, a part of which is absorbed by the phosphor and converted to a broad band in the yellow region. Fast YAG:Ce-based scintillators, among other Ce-doped garnets with accelerated decay time, are promising option for particle physics experiments such as High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider [2]. In YAG:Ce performing as a scintillator, many electron-hole pairs are created by a single high-energy photon or particle. After relaxation, the electrons and holes migrate, separately or as excitons, to the Ce^{3+} ions, where they recombine radiatively. A part of the electron hole pairs are captured by nonradiative recombination centers, another part

might be affected by trapping at shallow defect levels. The electron trapping in YAG:Ce is shown to decelerate the luminescence decay [3] and might also channel a part of the trapped electrons to deeper defect-related levels in the centers of nonradiative recombination. Several types of defects in YAG are identified as feasible electron traps theoretically [4] and observed in thermoluminescence experiments [3].

The influence of traps deteriorating the efficiency and timing properties of YAG:Ce scintillators might be mitigated by substituting a part of yttrium ions by gallium ions in the YAG lattice. This approach was initially exploited in Ce-doped lutetium aluminum garnet (LuAG:Ce). According to the experimental data and the first-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations, the introduction of gallium does not decrease the density of the trapping centers but rather buries the trapping levels in the conduction band as a result of a gradual shifting of the bottom of the conduction band down in energy [5]. An increase in the light yield by 30% as the gallium content x in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ is increased to $x \approx 0.4$ was demonstrated by Sidletskiy et al. [6]. The observed continuous change in optical and luminescence properties as the Ga content x is increased up to ~ 0.6 and qualitatively different behavior afterwards was interpreted by the incorporation of Ga ions at different positions in the garnet lattice: at low Ga content, Ga^{3+} ions substitute Al^{3+} ions in tetrahedral positions, whereas the substitution of the Al^{3+} ions in octahedral positions becomes increasingly important at higher x values [7]. Currently, it is generally accepted that the major effect of Ga in the lattice of YGAG:Ce and other Ce-doped multicomponent garnets is the downshift of the conduction band burying the trapping levels [8]. The deterioration of the emission properties at high Ga content is explained by the substantially enhanced thermal quenching as the potential barrier for the depopulation of the emitting level $5d^1$ of Ce^{3+} decreases due to the downshift of the bottom of the conduction band [9]. Shifting the energy of the emitting $5d^1$ level of the emitting Ce^{3+} ion down by the introduction of gadolinium into the multicomponent garnet increases the barrier. This approach led to the development of gallium aluminum gadolinium garnet (GAGG:Ce) [10–12] with an outstanding light yield and other competitive scintillation properties approaching theoretical limits [13]. The scintillation properties can be further improved by aliovalent codoping [14,15]. The localization of nonequilibrium carriers due to composition fluctuations in the multicomponent garnet lattice are also beneficial for the scintillator [16,17]. However, the scintillation decay time of GAGG:Ce scintillator is still too long

for many future applications in high energy physics experiments and medical imaging. The decay can be accelerated by heavy codoping, though at the expense of the light yield [18].

In the current study, we investigate the limits for achieving a fast emission decay time in Ce-doped Gd-free YAG garnets by optimizing the content of Ga as a substitute of Al in the lattice.

2. Experimental

2.1. Samples

Eight samples of $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ single crystals with Ga content x ranging from 0 to 1 were prepared after growing 100 mm long boules of ~30 mm in diameter by the Czochralski method in iridium crucible. Oxides Y_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , Ga_2O_3 , and CeO_2 of 99.99% were used as raw materials for the growth. YAG:Ce crystals were grown from stoichiometric melt, whereas 1% of Ga_2O_3 in excess to the stoichiometric ratio was taken in the melt when growing Ga-containing crystals to compensate ignition loss. 1 mol.% of CeO_2 was added in the melt for all the crystals grown. The crystals were grown in Ar atmosphere with added 1% of oxygen to inhibit melt evaporation. After the growth, all the crystals were annealed at 1500⁰C in oxygen atmosphere to compensate oxygen vacancies formed during the growth in inert atmosphere.

2.2. Characterization techniques

Time-resolved photoluminescence spectroscopy experiments were carried out using a spectroscopic setup consisting of spectrometer *Andor Kymera 193i*, a *Hamamatsu* back-thinned Charge-Coupled Device (BT-CCD), Time Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) module SPC-130 of *Becker&Hickl*, and a cooled photomultiplier tube PMC-150. A Yb:KGW laser *Pharos* of *Light Conversion* (pulse duration of 250 fs) was used as an excitation source. The initial emission wavelength of 1030 nm was converted and tuned to selectively excite the levels of activator ion Ce^{3+} by using optical parametric amplifier (*Orpheus*, *Light Conversion*) and harmonics generators. The overall time resolution in these measurements was 200 ps. The measurements were performed in liquid-nitrogen cryosystem of *Cryo Industries* at various temperatures fixed in the range from 80 to 600 K.

The quantum efficiency was extracted according to the three-measurement method [19] and using a 6-inch-diameter integrating sphere (*Gigahertz Optik*) coated with BaSO₄.

Experiments of cathodoluminescence (CL) spectroscopy with temporal resolution of 100 ps were carried out using spectrometric system *Chronos of Attolight*. The samples were excited by electrons accelerated at a voltage of 10 kV. Short pulses of the electrons were generated by the electron gun triggered by sub-10-ps pulses of *aeroPULSE PS* laser of *NKT Photonics*. A Cassegrain-type objective was used to collect the luminescence into spectrometer *Horiba iHR 320*. *Andor Newton 920* Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) camera was used for detection in spatial mapping, whereas the luminescence transients were recorded using *Hamamatsu C10910* streak camera. Surface morphology was studied using images obtained by the *Chronos* system operated in the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) mode.

3. Results

3.1. Absorption spectra

Absorption spectra of the samples under study are presented in Fig. 1. They have two distinct bands due to optical transitions between the ground state $^2F_{5/2}$ and two lowest excited states, $5d^1$ and $5d^2$, of ion Ce³⁺. One more Ce-related absorption band can be traced on the slope of the broad band in the UV region that is usually interpreted as a charge transfer absorption band related to ions Ce⁴⁺. The intensities of Ce³⁺ absorption bands depend on the total content of cerium and on the share of the cerium ions in the valence state Ce⁴⁺, which were identified in oxyorthosilicate and garnet-type hosts using X-ray Absorption Near Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) [14,20].

The energies corresponding to the peak positions of the absorption bands observed are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with various Ga content x (indicated).

Table 1. Peak energies (in eV) of absorption bands due to optical transitions to $5d^1$ and $5d^2$ of Ce^{3+} as a function of Ga content x in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$.

Ga content, x	0	0.16	0.36	0.66	0.75	0.8	0.85	1
To $5d^1$	2.71	2.84	2.92	2.92	2.9	2.92	2.95	2.99
To $5d^2$	3.65	3.59	3.56	3.55	3.56	3.57	3.55	3.53

3.2. Evolution of photoluminescence with temperature

The photoluminescence spectra of all the samples studied were measured at different temperatures fixed in the range from 90 to 750 K. The samples were excited resonantly to the emitting level $5d^1$ of Ce^{3+} ion. The typical spectra for three $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ samples with $x = 0, 0.85,$ and 1 are presented in Fig. 2. As expected for Ce^{3+} emission, two strongly overlapping bands due to the optical transitions from $5d_1$ to two ground levels $F_{7/2}$ and $F_{5/2}$ are observed in $Y_3Al_5O_{12}:Ce$ samples. The shape of the compound spectrum changes due to broadening of the two bands as the temperature is increases. The same features are observed also in the spectra of $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with Ga content x increasing up to ~ 0.8 , just the thermal quenching of the luminescence becomes more pronounced in the samples with larger x . In addition, a spectral component in far red region becomes more evident as the emission of Ce^{3+} is quenched. The luminescence spectrum substantially changes and its intensity drastically drops in $Y_3Ga_5O_{12}:Ce$ (see Fig.2c).

Fig. 2. Photoluminescence spectra at resonant excitation to the lowest excited level $5d_1$ of Ce^{3+} in $Y_3Al_5O_{12}:Ce$ (a), $Y_3(Al_{0.16}Ga_{0.84})_5O_{12}:Ce$ (b), and $Y_3Ga_5O_{12}:Ce$ (c) at various temperatures (indicated), temperature dependences of photoluminescence intensity at excitation to $5d_1$ (d) and $5d^2$ (e) levels of Ce^{3+} ion in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with different Ga content x (indicated). The lines are fits using Eq. (1).

The spectral features are similar in all the samples also at resonant excitation to the second excited Ce^{3+} level $5d^2$. Meanwhile, the temperature dependences of luminescence intensity at excitation to $5d_1$ and $5d^2$ exhibit different behavior. The dependences are provided in Fig. 2 (d, e) as intensity V versus reciprocal temperature T to test, whether the dependences obey the Arrhenius equation expected when the temperature dependence is caused by the thermal depopulation of the emitting level over a single energy barrier E_a :

$$V = \frac{V_0}{1 + A \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{k_B T}\right)}. \quad (1)$$

Here, V_0 is the intensity at low temperatures ($kT \ll E_a$), A is a fitting constant, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

At excitation to $5d^1$ (see Fig. 2d), the dependences for the four samples with the lowest Ga content can be fairly well fitted with the Arrhenius equation (1). The extracted activation energies are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Activation energies for thermal quenching in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with Ga content x , extracted using temperature dependences of photoluminescence intensity (second column) and decay time (third column).		
x	E_a , meV; intensity	E_a , meV; decay time
0	684±94	681 ± 63
0.16	628±85	642 ± 60
0.36	534±49	421 ± 29
0.66	333±31	386 ± 14

The temperature dependences for the samples with a higher Ga content do not fit equation (1), probably, as a result of more complicated mechanisms of thermal quenching.

The PL temperature dependences at excitation to $5d^2$ level that is presumably located in the conduction band are presented in Fig. 2e. In YAG:Ce without Ga, the increase in temperature up to 300 K results in an increase of luminescence intensity. This trend can also be traced in low-Ga-content $Y_3(Al_{0.16}Ga_{0.84})_5O_{12}:Ce$. The further increase in Ga content initially results in the temperature dependence of luminescence intensity obeying the Arrhenius equation, whereas the samples with Ga content above $x = 0.66$ exhibit substantial deviations from equation (1).

Photoluminescence kinetics at the band peak position were measured at temperatures fixed in the range from 90 to 750 K for all the samples studied. They are illustrated for two samples in Fig. 3. The PL decay in YAG:Ce can be fairly well described by a single exponent in the entire temperature range studied. The decay in samples with increasing Ga content exhibits deviations from the single exponent, especially at elevated temperatures, however, the major initial part of the PL intensity decays exponentially. Thus, we estimated the characteristic decay time in all the samples and at all temperatures as the time period corresponding to a decrease in intensity by a factor of $1/e$.

Fig. 3. Decay of normalized photoluminescence at resonant excitation to the lowest excited level $5d_1$ of Ce^{3+} in $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ (a) and $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{0.16}\text{Ga}_{0.84})_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ (b) at different temperatures (indicated), temperature dependences of photoluminescence decay time at excitation to $5d^1$ (c) and $5d^2$ (d) levels of Ce^{3+} ion in $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x)_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ with different Ga content x (indicated). The lines are fits using Eq. (1).

The temperature dependences of the decay time in all samples studied are presented in Fig. 3 (c, d). The dependences for the four samples with the lowest Ga content can be well fitted using the Arrhenius equation (1) with V and V_0 as the decay time and its constant value at low temperatures. The extracted activation energies are listed in Table 1. The dependencies for the samples with higher x values exhibit significant deviations from equation (1).

3.3. Internal quantum efficiency

The room-temperature quantum yield (QY) defined as a ratio of the number of photons emitted by activator ions Ce^{3+} to the number of the excitation photons absorbed by the ions was measured at photoexcitation of Ce^{3+} to levels $5d^1$ and $5d^2$. The results for $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x)_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ with different Ga content are presented in Fig. 4. The QY slightly increases with Ga content increasing up to $x \approx 0.5$ and drops abruptly at $x > 0.7$. The most significant increase in QY is between the samples with $x = 0$ and $x = 0.2$, whereas the QY value of 30% for the sample without Ga is untypically low for

YAG:Ce, probably because of the growth conditions optimized for growing Ga-containing samples.

Fig. 4. Quantum yield of $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ as a function of Ga content x at resonant photoexcitation to levels $5d^1$ and $5d^2$ of Ce^{3+} .

3.4. Cathodoluminescence

As for the PL spectra, the room-temperature cathodoluminescence (CL) spectra are dominated by Ce^{3+} emission in all samples studied, except the YGG:Ce sample (see Fig. 5a). The main CL band experiences a blue shift as the Ga content increases. In addition, an emission band peaked at ~ 3.8 eV is also observed. The band is most intense in YAG:Ce without Ga, is suppressed at moderate Ga content and becomes dominant in a weak emission of YGG:Ce. Emission bands in this spectral range have been observed in YAG:Ce luminescence spectra under synchrotron radiation [21,22], in CL spectra of $Y_3Al_{5-x}Ga_xO_{12}:Ce$ [23] and are interpreted by the radiative recombination of excitons localized at Y_{Al} antisite defects or luminescence of F^+ centers.

The Ce^{3+} emission is still dominant in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with $x = 0.85$, but is hardly traced in $Y_3Ga_5O_{12}:Ce$. In this sample with all Al ions substituted by Ga ions, a new band peaked at 2 eV emerges.

Fig. 5. Cathodoluminescence spectra (a) and decay kinetics (b) in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with different Ga content x (indicated).

The increase in Ga content results in faster CL decay (see Fig. 5b). The CL in $Y_3Al_5O_{12}:Ce$ without Ga decays exponentially with a decay constant of 92 ns. In addition to this decay component, the Ga containing samples exhibit a fast decay component with increasingly faster decay rate and contribution as the Ga content increases. The characteristic decay time of this fast component was estimated as the time period corresponding to a decrease in intensity by a factor of $1/e$. The values of the decay times for the samples with different Ga content are presented in Fig. 6(a).

The spectrally and temporally integrated intensities of Ce^{3+} cathodoluminescence in the samples with different Ga content are also presented in Fig. 6(a). The intensities slightly decrease with x increasing up to approximately 0.7 and sharply drops afterwards. This behavior is in line with the Ga content dependence of the characteristic decay time of the fast CL decay component [as evident in Fig. 6(a)].

No intensity increase with peak intensity at $x = 0.4 - 0.5$, which has been observed under X-ray [6] and synchrotron [7] radiation, was observed in our CL experiments. The different behavior might be caused by a nonlinearity in CL response due to a higher excitation density in our CL measurements. To test this hypothesis, we studied the excitation intensity dependence of CL intensity.

Fig. 6. (a) Cathodoluminescence intensity (squares, left axis) and decay time (circles, right axis) in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with different Ga content x . Figure of merit $\sqrt{\tau/LY}$ values (see text for details) are presented in the inset. (b) Cathodoluminescence intensity in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with different Ga content x at different electron probe currents (indicated). (c) Dependences of cathodoluminescence intensity (points) on electron beam current in the samples with different Ga content (indicated). Lines are the best fits of the dependences with power law $I(j) \propto j^\alpha$ (α values are indicated with the corresponding line).

The dependence of spectrally and temporally integrated CL intensity on the electron beam current is presented in Fig. 6(c). The current was varied by defocusing the electron beam on an aperture behind which the electrons were finally focused onto the sample surface. The excitation spot size was maintained constant. Thus, the number of electrons exciting the sample was in direct proportion to the current. The dependence of CL intensity I on current j is slightly sublinear and can be approximated as $I(j) \propto j^\alpha$. The power factor α decreases from 0.84 to 0.71 as the Ga content increases from 0 to 0.85. The CL intensity dependences on excitation intensity for different samples are presented in Fig. 6(b).

The CL intensity dependence on Ga content x in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ measured at different electron beam currents exhibit a fast drop in high-Ga-content samples with $x = 0.8$. Meanwhile,

the major difference in the dependences is the initial increase in intensity when small amounts of Ga are introduced. The increase becomes more pronounced with decreasing excitation intensity.

4. Discussion

The analysis of the measured absorption spectra and the temperature dependences of PL parameters enabled us to estimate the influence of Ga content on energy structure of $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$. For the low-Ga-content samples, our measurements of temperature dependence of PL intensity and decay time shows that the thermal quenching proceeds over a single energy barrier. First of all, two types of quenching processes leading to the decrease in the luminescence intensity of YAGG:Ce scintillator at increasing temperature have to be considered: intracenter non-radiative decay and thermal quenching due to the activation of electrons from Ce^{3+} level $5d_1$ to the conduction band. The activation energy for the intracenter non-radiative decay can be estimated as $E_{a,int} = \frac{(E_{^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow 5d_1} - S\hbar\Omega)^2}{4S\hbar\Omega}$ [24], where $E_{^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow 5d_1}$ is the energy of transition $^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow 5d_1$ without phonon interaction, S is the Huang-Rhys factor, and $\hbar\Omega$ is the general optical phonon energy. We extracted $E_{^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow 5d_1}$ at different gallium content by using the measured peak positions of the absorption band due to transition $^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow 5d_1$ of Ce^{3+} in YAGG:Ce crystals under this study and subtracting the energy shift $S\hbar\Omega$. The value of S was taken to be 6 [25], and $\hbar\Omega = 40$ meV was obtained from the best fits of the cerium absorption spectra. The $E_{^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow 5d_1}$ values range from 2.47 eV to 2.75 eV at gallium content varying from 0 to 1. The obtained minimal value of $E_{a,int}$ equals 5.18 eV. Thus, the parabolic branches of cerium levels $5d_1$ and $^2F_{5/2}$ in the configuration diagram have a cross point deep in the conduction band, so that the intracenter quenching in these crystals can be neglected.

At resonant excitation to $5d_1$, when no excitation transfer is expected, the quantum yield has a bell-shaped dependence on Ga content (see Fig. 4). This behavior is in line with the light yield dependence measured under X-ray excitation and showing a 130% peak increase in the dependence at $x = 0.4$ [6] and the bell-shaped dependence of cathodo- and radio-luminescence intensity with the peak at $x \approx 0.5$ [7]. The increase in luminescence intensity with increasing Ga content was interpreted by the elimination of trapping. The mechanism caused by limited carrier diffusion due to composition fluctuations suggested to interpret similar intensity enhancement in $Lu_xY_{1-x}AlO_3:Ce$ scintillators [26] might also be important. Both the mechanisms are feasible at

excitation by high-energy photons. However, we do observe the increase in luminescence intensity with increasing x even at the excitation of Ce^{3+} resonantly to the emitting level $5d_1$, when no trapping is expected. Moreover, the barrier for thermal depopulation constantly decreases with x (see Table 2), at least for x of up to 0.6. Consequently, an additional mechanism of emission enhancement as Ga is introduced is in action and affects directly the Ce^{3+} . It is feasible that defects in YAG lattice can act not only as trapping centers, but a part of them might form complexes with Ce^{3+} acting as nonradiative recombination centers. These „dark Ce ions“ do not participate in light emission and have no influence on the luminescence decay kinetics. However, they capture nonequilibrium electrons or absorb photons at resonant photoexcitation and facilitate nonradiative recombination. The larger fraction of excitations channeled to nonradiative recombination decreases the luminescence efficiency. The introduction of Ga presumably heals such defects, decreases the concentration of „dark Ce ions“, and increases the light yield. It is known that antisite defects [27] and oxygen vacancies act as electron traps in garnets [4,27,28]. The same defects, just in close proximity of Ce^{3+} ions, might presumably build the complexes acting as the centers of nonradiative recombination. Revealing the structure of these complexes and the mechanisms of their healing by Ga need a dedicated investigation.

The $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x)_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ samples with Ga content above ~ 0.6 have more than one channel for thermal quenching. The level of Ga^{3+} perturbed by the neighboring Ce^{3+} ion [9] or some other electron traps [5] could act as levels below the bottom of the valence band and serve for channeling the electrons from the emitting Ce^{3+} level $5d_1$ to the route of nonradiative recombination.

At excitation with high energy photons, as in real operation in radiation detection, the performance of scintillator material is additionally affected by excitation relaxation and transfer to the emitting centers. First of all, our study of CL intensity dependence on the current in the electron beam intensity shows that the CL intensity sublinearly depends on the excitation intensity, and the deviation from a linear dependence becomes stronger when the Ga content in $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x)_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ increases. A weak sublinearity was also observed in the luminescence intensity dependence on excitation intensity at the highest intensities in our photoluminescence experiments: we performed the PL measurements at the excitation intensities in the range from $4 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ to $20 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$; the sublinearity starts to be obvious above $\sim 10 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$. The most straightforward origin of the nonlinearity is saturation of certain recombination or trapping centers. However, the saturation of trapping centers or the centers of nonradiative recombination would lead to superlinearity in the

dependence of emission intensity versus excitation intensity. Instead, we observe a sublinear dependence that might be interpreted by the saturation of the emitting Ce^{3+} centers. Their concentration of ~ 0.1 at% relatively to Y^{3+} in the samples studied corresponds to the density of 10^{19} cm^{-3} . The estimated initial density of electron-hole pairs at the highest pulse energy used in our PL experiments is $\sim 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Thus, the saturation is quite feasible in PL experiments. Meanwhile, even a rough estimate of the electron-hole pair density in CL experiments requires performing Monte Carlo simulations and knowing material parameters that are unavailable. However, the CL intensity dependence on excitation intensity (probe current) has a distinct feature evidencing that the sublinearity of this dependence is caused not by saturation of the emitting centers: the dependence of CL intensity on current follows the same power law $I(j) \propto j^\alpha$ in a wide range of j (from 50 fA to 800 pA). From the point of view of applications, it is important that the nonlinearity has to be taken into account when studying the luminescence intensity, and the optimization of Ga content in YAGG:Ce scintillator has to be performed at the excitation conditions corresponding to those in exploitation.

Cathodoluminescence decay time and intensity at high excitation intensities are compared for $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x)_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ with different Ga content x in Fig. 6. Both dependences have similar shapes: a moderate decrease at x increasing up to ~ 0.7 and a sharp decrease afterwards. It is worth noting that the decrease in the decay time is faster than that of intensity. This is favorable for faster scintillation response. The most common figure of merit to describe the scintillator response time is the Coincidence Time Resolution (CTR). For Ce-activated garnet-type scintillators, the dependence of CTR on the luminescence decay time τ and the number of photons detected (N_{ph}) is quite well described as $CTR \propto \sqrt{\tau/N_{ph}}$ [29–31]. In our experiments, CL intensity is proportional to the number of photons detected N_{ph} , so we use the intensity to estimate τ/N_{ph} . The incorporation of Ga in $\text{Y}_3(\text{Al}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x)_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ up to $x \approx 0.7$ results in a decrease in the ratio τ/N_{ph} even at high excitation intensities. Thus, the CTR becomes shorter indicating a faster scintillator response. At lower excitation intensities, the N_{ph} dependence on x becomes flatter, and the response time is further improved.

5. Conclusions

Fitting the temperature dependences of photoluminescence intensity and decay time with Arrhenius expression enabled us to extract the activation energies for thermal quenching in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with Ga content x up to 0.66. The extracted activation energies and absorption spectra led us to a conclusion that the thermal quenching due to the activation of electrons from Ce^{3+} level $5d_1$ to the conduction band dominates over the intracenter non-radiative decay. The luminescence in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with elevated Ga content have more than one channel for thermal quenching.

Our results show that the introduction of gallium into scintillator $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ affects both luminescence efficiency and decay time. Photoluminescence intensity as a function of temperature evidences the influence of trapping centers that is eliminated with the introduction of even a low amount ($x = 0.16$ in our sample studied) of Ga. Meanwhile, the barrier for thermal depopulation of the emitting level $5d_1$ of the ion Ce^{3+} constantly decreases with increasing Ga content x . Thus, the further increase in the light yield observed at the resonant excitation to the $5d_1$ level of Ce^{3+} with x increasing up to ~ 0.6 has additional mechanism, most probably, the conversion of „dark Ce ions“, which consist of Ce^{3+} associated with defects, to emitting ions Ce^{3+} .

When measured in a wide dynamic range, the luminescence intensity dependence on excitation intensity is sublinear. The sublinearity is stronger in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ with higher x . Therefore, the Ga content in YAGG:Ce scintillator has to be optimized at the excitation conditions in intended exploitation.

For any excitation intensities, the ratio between the luminescence decay time and the light yield decreases with increasing Ga content. As a result, the coincidence time resolution parameter becomes shorter indicating that the performance of scintillator $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ is faster with Ga content x increasing up to ~ 0.7 . From the practical point, it is attractive that the luminescence decay time in $Y_3(Al_{1-x}Ga_x)_5O_{12}:Ce$ scintillators can be tuned by Ga content, whereas the luminescence of the compound with composition $x = 0.85$ exhibits a very fast decay time below 20 ns, promising for particle physics experiments at colliders.

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